

LEAD IDENTIFICATION AGAINST MULTI DRUG RESISTANT ESKAPE PATHOGENS ON E. FAECIUM USING INHOUSE HERBAL MEDICINAL DATABASE

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Abstract

Colorectal cancer or Colon cancer is the third most common cancer in the Western hemisphere and the incidence increases with the age. Most Colorectal cancers are localized with or without lymph node metastases where up to 20% of the patients present with metastatic disease, most commonly to the liver. Surgery is the only remedial therapy for localized colorectal cancer. The 5EYF Protein molecule of Enterococcus faecium is targeted with 1000 ligand molecules of herbal compounds and after that ADME prediction is done. The aim of the present work is to provide an overview of medicinal plants compounds on colon cancer using Enterococcus faecium and find a therapeutic drug using 5EYF protein molecule.

Keywords: Colon Cancer, Enterococcus faecium, Autodock Vina, Pymol.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a disease in which some of the body's cells grow uncontrollably and spread to other parts of the body. Cancer can start almost anywhere in the human body, which is made up of trillions of cells. Normally, human cells grow and multiply (through a process called cell division) to form new cells as the body needs them. When cells grow old or become damaged, they die, and new cells take their place. Sometimes this orderly process breaks down, and abnormal or damaged cells grow and multiply when they shouldn't. These cells may form tumors, which are lumps of tissue. Tumors can be cancerous or not cancerous (benign). Cancerous tumors spread into, or invade, nearby tissues and can travel to distant places in the body to form new tumors (a process called metastasis). Cancerous tumors may also be called malignant tumors. Many cancers form solid tumors, but cancers of the blood, such as leukemias, generally do not. Benign tumors do not spread into, or invade, nearby tissues. When removed, benign tumors usually don't grow back, whereas cancerous tumors sometimes do. Benign tumors can sometimes be quite large, however. Some can cause serious symptoms or be life threatening, such as benign tumors in the brain.

Cancer cells differ from normal cells in many ways. For instance, cancer cells: grow in the absence of signals telling them to grow. Normal cells only grow when they receive such signals. Ignore signals that normally tell cells to stop dividing or to die (a process known as programmed cell death, or apoptosis). Invade into nearby areas and spread to other areas of the body. Normal cells stop growing when they encounter other cells, and most normal cells do not move around the body. Tell blood vessels to grow toward tumors. These blood vessels supply tumors with oxygen and nutrients and remove waste products from tumors. Hide from the immune system. The

immune system normally eliminates damaged or abnormal cells. Trick the immune system into helping cancer cells stay alive and grow. For instance, some cancer cells convince immune cells to protect the tumor instead of attacking it. Accumulate multiple changes in their chromosomes, such as duplications and deletions of chromosome parts. Some cancer cells have double the normal number of chromosomes. Rely on different kinds of nutrients than normal cells. In addition, some cancer cells make energy from nutrients in a different way than most normal cells. This lets cancer cells grow more quickly. Many times, cancer cells rely so heavily on these abnormal behaviors that they can't survive without them. Researchers have taken advantage of this fact, developing therapies that target the abnormal features of cancer cells. For example, some cancer therapies prevent blood vessels from growing toward tumors, essentially starving the tumor of needed nutrients. Cancer is a genetic disease—that is, it is caused by changes to genes that control the way our cells function, especially how they grow and divide. Genetic changes that cause cancer can happen because: of errors that occur as cells divide. Of damage to DNA caused by harmful substances in the environment, such as the chemicals in tobacco smoke and ultraviolet rays from the sun. (Our Cancer Causes and Prevention section has more information.) They were inherited from our parents. The body normally eliminates cells with damaged DNA before they turn cancerous. But the body's ability to do so goes down as we age. This is part of the reason why there is a higher risk of cancer later in life. Each person's cancer has a unique combination of genetic changes. As the cancer continues to grow, additional changes will occur. Even within the same tumor, different cells may have different genetic changes.

The genetic changes that contribute to cancer tend to affect three main types of genes—proto-oncogenes, tumor suppressor genes, and DNA repair genes. These changes are sometimes called “drivers” of cancer. Proto-oncogenes are involved in normal cell growth and division. However, when these genes are altered in certain ways or are more active than normal, they may become cancer-causing genes (or oncogenes), allowing cells to grow and survive when they should not. Tumor suppressor genes are also involved in controlling cell growth and division. Cells with certain alterations in tumor suppressor genes may divide in an uncontrolled manner. DNA repair genes are involved in fixing damaged DNA. Cells with mutations in these genes tend to develop additional mutations in other genes and changes in their chromosomes, such as duplications and deletions of chromosome parts. Together, these mutations may cause the cells to become cancerous. As scientists have learned more about the molecular changes that lead to cancer, they have found that certain mutations commonly occur in many types of cancer. Now there are many cancer treatments available that target gene mutations found in cancer. A few of these treatments can be used by anyone with a cancer that has the targeted mutation, no matter where the cancer started growing. When Cancer Spread. A cancer that has spread from the place where it first formed to another place in the body is called metastatic cancer. The process by which cancer cells spread to other parts of the body is called metastasis. Metastatic cancer has the same name and the same type of cancer cells as the original, or primary, cancer. For example, breast cancer that forms a metastatic tumor in the lung is metastatic breast cancer, not lung cancer. Under a microscope, metastatic cancer cells generally look the same as cells of the original cancer. Moreover, metastatic cancer cells and cells of the original cancer usually have some molecular features in common, such as the presence of specific chromosome changes. In some cases,

treatment may help prolong the lives of people with metastatic cancer. In other cases, the primary goal of treatment for metastatic cancer is to control the growth of the cancer or to relieve symptoms it is causing. Metastatic tumors can cause severe damage to how the body functions, and most people who die of cancer die of metastatic disease. Tissue Changes that are not Cancer. Not every change in the body's tissues is cancer. Some tissue changes may develop into cancer if they are not treated, however. Here are some examples of tissue changes that are not cancer but, in some cases, are monitored because they could become cancer: Hyperplasia occurs when cells within a tissue multiply faster than normal and extra cells build up. However, the cells and the way the tissue is organized still look normal under a microscope. Hyperplasia can be caused by several factors or conditions, including chronic irritation. Dysplasia is a more advanced condition than hyperplasia. In dysplasia, there is also a buildup of extra cells. But the cells look abnormal and there are changes in how the tissue is organized.

In general, the more abnormal the cells and tissue look, the greater the chance that cancer will form. Some types of dysplasia may need to be monitored or treated, but others do not. An example of dysplasia is an abnormal mole (called a dysplastic nevus) that forms on the skin. A dysplastic nevus can turn into melanoma, although most do not. Carcinoma in situ is an even more advanced condition. Although it is sometimes called stage 0 cancer, it is not cancer because the abnormal cells do not invade nearby tissue the way that cancer cells do. But because some carcinomas in situ may become cancer, they are usually treated.

Types of Cancer:

There are more than 100 types of cancer. Types of cancer are usually named for the organs or tissues where the cancers form. For example, lung cancer starts in the lung, and brain cancer starts in the brain. Cancers also may be described by the type of cell that formed them, such as an epithelial cell or a squamous cell.

a. Carcinoma - Carcinomas are the most common type of cancer. They are formed by epithelial cells, which are the cells that cover the inside and outside surfaces of the body. There are many types of epithelial cells, which often have a column-like shape when viewed under a microscope. Carcinomas that begin in different epithelial cell types have specific names: Adenocarcinoma is a cancer that forms in epithelial cells that produce fluids or mucus. Tissues with this type of epithelial cell are sometimes called glandular tissues. Most cancers of the breast, colon, and prostate are adenocarcinomas. Basal cell carcinoma is a cancer that begins in the lower or basal (base) layer of the epidermis, which is a person's outer layer of skin. Squamous cell carcinoma is a cancer that forms in squamous cells, which are epithelial cells that lie just beneath the outer surface of the skin. Squamous cells also line many other organs, including the stomach, intestines, lungs, bladder, and kidneys. Squamous cells look flat, like fish scales, when viewed under a microscope. Squamous cell carcinomas are sometimes called epidermoid carcinomas. Transitional cell carcinoma is a cancer that forms in a type of epithelial tissue called transitional epithelium, or urothelium. This tissue, which is made up of many layers of epithelial cells that can get bigger and smaller, is found in the linings of the bladder, ureters, and part of the kidneys (renal pelvis), and a few other organs. Some cancers of the bladder, ureters, and kidneys are transitional cell carcinomas.

b. Sarcoma- Soft tissue sarcoma forms in soft tissues of the body, including muscle, tendons, fat, blood vessels, lymph vessels, nerves, and tissue around joints. Sarcomas are cancers that form in bone and soft tissues, including muscle, fat, blood vessels, lymph vessels, and fibrous tissue (such as tendons and ligaments). Osteosarcoma is the most common cancer of bone. The most common types of soft tissue sarcoma are leiomyosarcoma, Kaposi sarcoma, malignant fibrous histiocytoma, liposarcoma, and dermatofibrosarcoma protuberans.

c. Leukemia- Cancers that begin in the blood-forming tissue of the bone marrow are called leukemias. These cancers do not form solid tumors. Instead, large numbers of abnormal white blood cells (leukemia cells and leukemic blast cells) build up in the blood and bone marrow, crowding out normal blood cells. The low level of normal blood cells can make it harder for the body to get oxygen to its tissues, control bleeding, or fight infections. There are four common types of leukemia, which are grouped based on how quickly the disease gets worse (acute or chronic) and on the type of blood cell the cancer starts in (lymphoblastic or myeloid). Acute forms of leukemia grow quickly and chronic forms grow more slowly.

Lymphoma- Lymphoma is cancer that begins in lymphocytes (T cells or B cells). These are disease-fighting white blood cells that are part of the immune system. In lymphoma, abnormal lymphocytes build up in lymph nodes and lymph vessels, as well as in other organs of the body. There are two main types of lymphoma: Hodgkin lymphoma – People with this disease have abnormal lymphocytes that are called Reed-Sternberg cells. These cells usually form from B cells. Non-Hodgkin lymphoma – This is a large group of cancers that start in lymphocytes. The cancers can grow quickly or slowly and can form from B cells or T cells.

d. Multiple Myeloma- Multiple myeloma is cancer that begins in plasma cells, another type of immune cell. The abnormal plasma cells, called myeloma cells, build up in the bone marrow and form tumors in bones all through the body. Multiple myeloma is also called plasma cell myeloma and Kahler disease.

Melanoma- Melanoma is cancer that begins in cells that become melanocytes, which are specialized cells that make melanin (the pigment that gives skin its color). Most melanomas form on the skin, but melanomas can also form in other pigmented tissues, such as the eye.

Brain and Spinal Cord Tumors- There are different types of brain and spinal cord tumors. These tumors are named based on the type of cell in which they formed and where the tumor first formed in the central nervous system. For example, an astrocytic tumor begins in star-shaped brain cells called astrocytes, which help keep nerve cells healthy. Brain tumors can be benign (not cancer) or malignant (cancer).

Other Types of Tumors

e. Germ Cell Tumors- Germ cell tumors are a type of tumor that begins in the cells that give rise to sperm or eggs. These tumors can occur almost anywhere in the body and can be either benign or malignant.

f. Neuroendocrine Tumors- Neuroendocrine tumors form from cells that release hormones into the blood in response to a signal from the nervous system. These tumors, which may make higher-

than-normal amounts of hormones, can cause many different symptoms. Neuroendocrine tumors may be benign or malignant.

g. Carcinoid Tumors- Carcinoid tumors are a type of neuroendocrine tumor. They are slow-growing tumors that are usually found in the gastrointestinal system (most often in the rectum and small intestine). Carcinoid tumors may spread to the liver or other sites in the body, and they may secrete substances such as serotonin or prostaglandins, causing carcinoid syndrome.

h. Colorectal cancer- Colorectal cancer is the fourth most common cancer in men and the third most common cancer in women. [1-8]

Colon cancer is the type of cancer that begins in the large intestine (colon). Lynch syndrome (formerly known as hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer, HNPCC) and familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP) are autosomal dominant genetic disorders that comprise the majority of these. Other less common familial CRC syndromes include the hamartomatous syndromes, hyperplastic polyposis syndromes, the autosomal recessive MYH-associated polyposis syndrome, and familial juvenile polyposis. Although the global incidence of heritable CRC is relatively low when compared to their sporadic counterpart, early identification of such high-risk individuals and their families is important in order to commence timely screening and surveillance programs.

Lynch syndrome is caused by germline mutations in DNA mismatch repair (MMR) genes MLH1, MSH2, MSH6 and PMS2. Also genomic rearrangements within the epithelial cell adhesion molecule gene EPCAM can lead to silencing of the closely linked MSH2 gene in EPCAM-expressing tissues. CRCs in Lynch syndrome are characterized by an adenoma-carcinoma progression ratio of 1:1 (estimated adenoma-cancer transformation time 1–3 years), as compared to sporadic cases that have a ratio of 30:1 (estimated adenoma-cancer transformation time 8–17 years). If left untreated, the majority of polyps will become malignant as observed in approximately 70% of patients at age 70 and 80% of patients at 85 years. There is an increased incidence of metachronous and synchronous colon cancers with a second primary CRC developing in up to 30% after 10 years and 50% after 15 years. Lynch syndrome predisposes to extracolonic malignancies involving the endometrium, stomach, ovaries, small bowel, hepatobiliary epithelium, uroepithelial epithelium and brain [9-11]. The history of Lynch syndrome dates back to 1895 when Aldred Scott Warthin worked as the Chairman of the Department of Pathology at the University of Michigan, School of Medicine in Ann Arbor. Lynch syndrome patients have inherited at least one defective allele of a MMR gene. The normal function of the MMR proteins is to proofread the nucleotide sequence for potential base-base errors that occur during DNA synthesis. Microsatellites are short repetitive sequences that are distributed throughout the human genome. Defective MMR causes variations within the microsatellites, manifesting as a gain or loss in repeat length. This is described as microsatellite instability (MSI) [12 -15].

The colon is the final part of the digestive tract. Lynch syndrome (hereditary non-polyposis colon cancer) is caused by changes in genes that normally help a cell repair damaged DNA. A mutation in one of the DNA repair enzyme genes like MLH1, MSH2, MLH3 and MSH6 can

allow DNA errors to go unfixed. These errors will sometimes affect growth-regulating genes, which may lead to the development of cancer [16, 17]. Colorectal cancer is divided into five stages [Fig.1],

Fig 1. Colorectal cancer stages [18]

STAGE 0: The formation of abnormal growth starts where its appearance will be like small bumps or mushroom stalks.

STAGE 1: The cancer has penetrated the lining or mucosa, of the colon or rectum but hasn't spread to the organ walls.

STAGE 2: The cancer has spread to the walls of the colon or rectum but hasn't affected the lymph nodes or nearby tissues yet.

STAGE 3: The cancer has moved to the lymph nodes but not to other parts of the body yet. Usually, one to three lymph nodes are involved at this stage.

STAGE 4: The cancer has spread to the other distant organs, such as the liver or lungs [18].

Role of PDK1

Fig 2. PDK1 STRUCTURE

PDK1 (Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase 1) belongs to family of Serine/threonine kinase [Fig 2]. It is a kinase enzyme which acts to inactivate the enzyme pyruvate dehydrogenase by phosphorylating it using ATP. PDK1 knock down the adherence of colorectal cells. Elevated expression of PDK leads to a shift in glucose metabolism towards glycolysis instead of oxidative phosphorylation [21]. Tumor cells prefer glycolysis (Warburg effect) during the proliferation and metastasis. The precise mechanism remains largely unknown [22]. Pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH) is a mitochondrial multi-enzyme complex that catalyzes the oxidative

decarboxylation of pyruvate and is one of the major enzymes responsible for the regulation of homeostasis of carbohydrate [23, 24].

Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinases (PDKs) could regulate PDH phosphorylation which leads to the inactivation of PDH [25]. PDK1 has frequently increased expression in cancer cells including gastric cancer, colon cancer and acute myeloid leukemia [26-28]. In cancer cells, aerobic glycolysis is one of the most important metabolic processes even if there is enough oxygen [29]. This metabolic decision which diverts pyruvate and its precursors undergo other anabolic processes or convert to lactate for cancer cells are known as the Warburg effect [30]. Also, the intermediates support nucleic, lipid and protein synthesis during the rapid cell division. So, the Warburg effect supplies the high energy demands for cancer cell and biosynthesis materials. During these molecular adaptations, high pyruvate concentrations are maintained in cancer cells, which results in HIF-1 α stabilization [31]. Then HIF-1 α acts as a key mediator that transcriptionally regulates expression of a vast variety of genes to promote cell proliferation, migration and metastasis [32-34]. This article mainly focuses on PDK1 Where their role and its importance in the treatment of colon cancer.

Virtual screening using autodock

AutoDock is a suite of software for predicting the optimal bound conformations of ligands to proteins [35, 36]. The initial applications of AutoDock were in the analysis of binding modes and catalytic properties of protein and nucleic acid complexes [37, 38], and a typical study would include results from several dozen docking simulations. More recently, however, enhancements in the performance of AutoDock combined with the availability of high-speed computers and clusters of computers has allowed much larger experiments, where entire compound libraries are screened against pharmaceutically-relevant targets [39]

In this article, the virtual screening is done between ligands and protein [5EYF] and the computational binding between them is a great [Fig 3]. Computational docking is used to predict the binding modes of two or more molecules. Building on two decades of research, many successful methods for docking of ligands to macromolecular targets have been developed [40 – 47].

Fig 3. Preparing Autodock between ligands and proteins

2. OBJECTIVES

- To identify natural compounds from the herbal plants using virtual screening (Autodock vina).
- ADME (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion and Toxicity) predictions will be done for the natural compounds.
- To explore the binding mechanisms of the identified compounds using Pymol.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Historical background

The pyruvate dehydrogenase complex (PDC) is the key enzyme system in the body that catalyzes the oxidative decarboxylation of pyruvate to form acetyl coenzyme A. By serving as a crossroad between glycolysis and the tricarboxylic acid cycle, PDC plays a crucial role in aerobic metabolism [48]. PDC is comprised by three catalytic enzymes and their regulatory proteins: pyruvate dehydrogenase (E1), dihydrolipoamide acetyltransferase (E2), and dihydrolipoamide dehydrogenase (E3) [49]. PDC in eukaryotic cells of higher animals (such as humans) has dihydrolipoamide dehydrogenase binding protein (E3BP) and two regulatory enzymes, pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase (PDK) and pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphatase (PDP), as shown in Figure 1. The two types of enzymes, PDK and PDP, strictly regulate PDC activity by phosphorylation (inhibition) and dephosphorylation (activation) of serine residues 293, 300, and 232 of the E1 α subunit of heterotetramer pyruvate dehydrogenase [50]. PDKs, as the regulatory enzymes of pyruvate dehydrogenase (PDH), are located in the mitochondria, mainly distributed in mammals and play an important role in glycolysis.

Under normal conditions, pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphatase inhibits PDK and activates PDC, which then catalyzes pyruvate in the tricarboxylic acid cycle to produce a large amount of ATP to meet the energy needs of the body. Pyruvate is a precursor of glucose synthesis and maintains blood glucose levels during starvation. When the body is under starvation, PDK inhibits the activity of PDC, leading to the failure of decarboxylation and accumulation of pyruvate in the cytoplasm. Under certain pathological conditions, phosphorylation of PDC inhibits the activity of PDK. Phosphorylation of PDK inactivates PDC, and pyruvate cannot be completely oxidized or converted into fatty acids. The malignant transformation of cells and changes in metabolic pathways continuously activate PDK [51].

Pyruvate Dehydrogenase Kinase (PDK) is an important regulator of Pyruvate Dehydrogenase Complex (PDC), a mitochondrial complex consisting of multiple copies of three catalytic enzymes (E1p, E2p, and E3). Lester Reed and his Colleagues discovered regulation of Mammalian PDC by phosphorylation nearly half a century ago (Linn et al. 1969). Prior to that discovery, Negative feedback regulation by the products of the reaction catalyzed by PDC was carried out [52]. This work on, Lead Identification against colon cancer from In-house Herbal Medicinal Database has its origin, from the existing survey of literature. Keywords in the work, such as colon cancer, protein and plant molecular compounds were investigated thoroughly, in various literature databases, such as NCBI, PubMed, and Nature. Also, various computational methods such as Pharmacophore modeling and Virtual screening for the identification of plant compounds that are used against colon cancer for therapeutic purpose, has extensively been studied. There are some similar research articles that used rose herbal extract and made computational studies with colon cancer. These rose herbals are believed to create good flora and have good bacteria in our gut. This shows significance improvement with herbal plants. My article is similar, but instead of rose my article focuses on Nilavembu and Karisalankanni treating against *E. faecium*. In this case, Nilavembu and Karisalankanni are used in many research for purpose of treating infection or any other diseases. But there are no articles that used Karisalankanni or Nilavembu treating against colon cancer. This also includes, protein molecules of 5EYF. This 5EYF belongs to family of *Enterococcus faecium* which is a solute binding-protein that used in my article.

There is a research article that focuses on medicinal leaf that can be used as treatment for colorectal cancer. It explains that in vitro antibacterial activity of seven ethanolic extracts of spices against high level gentamicin resistant that isolated from human clinical samples. The plants used in their article is found to be as, cinnamon (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*), ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) which as activity on human samples that isolated. Cloves (*Syzygium aromaticum*) had effect on strain. Cardamom (*Elettaria cardamomum* Maton), black pepper (*Piper nigrum*), fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) had no effect in strains of human samples. They also explained about well diffusion assay that gives zone of inhibition for cinnamon, ginger, Cloves which is around 31-44 mm as radius [53]. This explains how effective with human cells that are treatable with these herbal leaves. Another article that explains use of pomegranate herbal extracts that treated with colon cancer. This pomegranate has some natural antioxidants that help to treat cancer. They also done molecular docking to see different ligands that interact with protein molecule of pomegranate. [54] They observed

some interesting happening between amino acids that showed how strong for treating colorectal cancer. The amino acids such as asparine and tyrosine are at high levels which changes pattern in antimicrobial activity. They also done well diffusion studies, to find Prescence of antibiotic that can be treated with E. faecium or any other bacteria.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

List of the computational software's which were carried out in the Dry lab,

- Open Babel,
- Autodock and Autodock Vina,
- Pymol,
- ADME Predictor from <https://omictools.com/admet-predictor-tool> [Online Software]

Database used:

- Plant compound's structure Database
- Protein – 5EYF (E.faecium)

The method involves molecular docking between ligand and protein. The ligands used here are, plant molecular compounds where 1000 compounds from 20 plant species were taken. This is done by virtual screening using Autodock Vina, to get good binding molecules which have higher binding affinity. Then, with the help of Pymol and Autodock, structures are identified based on similarity of the proteins and by using ADME prediction; these compounds are further reduced to four compounds. It was observed that, these four compounds (Ligand) showed higher binding affinity with 5EYF Protein.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interaction between 5EYF and Herbal medicinal compounds

This 5EYF is a solute binding protein and belongs to organism of E. faecium. The plant herbal compounds have the capacity to reduce naturally the abundance of colon cancer cells. In this case, the plant compounds ligands are approximately around 1000 compounds in different plant species (20 Species). Each has unique potential medicinal compounds. During Autodock Vina screening these are reduced to 100 compounds. After Screening, further reduced using ADME (“absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion”) prediction this reduces to four compounds which shows higher binding affinity and energy. Below is the RMSD Table [Fig 4],

Fig 4. Autodock virtual screening showing RMSD result values

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#
# O. Trott, A. J. Olson,
# AutoDock Vina: improving the speed and accuracy of docking
# with a new scoring function, efficient optimization and
# multithreading, Journal of Computational Chemistry 31 (2010)
# 455-461
#
# DOI 10.1002/jcc.21334
#
# Please see http://vina.scripps.edu for more information.
#####
WARNING: The search space volume > 27000 Angstrom^3 (See FAQ)
Output will be ligand_1_out.pdbqt
Detected 4 CPUs
Reading input ... done.
Setting up the scoring function ... done.
Analyzing the binding site ... done.
Using random seed: 1407847472
Performing random search ...
0% 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100%
|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|----|
*****
done.
Refining results ... done.

mode | affinity | dist from best mode
      | (kcal/mol) | rmsd l.b. | rmsd u.b.
-----+-----+-----+-----
  1   | -5.6      | 0.000     | 0.000
  2   | -5.6      | 1.025     | 3.915
  3   | -5.4      | 1.746     | 3.704
  4   | -5.3      | 2.147     | 4.840
  5   | -5.3      | 12.986    | 15.073
  6   | -5.2      | 14.518    | 16.505
  7   | -5.1      | 12.780    | 14.829
  8   | -5.0      | 1.185     | 4.275
  9   | -5.0      | 23.026    | 24.686
Writing output ... done.
```

This table shows, the first four compounds have higher binding values. Also, all the compounds have similar bonding structure.

- Using Pymol, similar binding poses with ligands (1, 6, 14, 54) for all the 4 compounds can be studied [Fig 5 – 9]. It indicates higher binding RMSD values around -5.6 (first affinity value).
- Between the bonds of amino acids and ligands, leucine, serine, asparine, tyrosine is found.
- Bond lengths between amino acids and ligand (1, 6, 21) is found to be 3.1Å and the bond lengths between amino acid and ligand (14, 54) is found to be 3.2 Å.
- The ADME Prediction, showed best binding pose for Compound 6, 4 – Imidazolidinone, 1- (1,1 – dimethyl ethyl)-3- imino -5,5 – diph with 5EYF receptor.
- This predicts again its best energy binding pose and its properties (also for molecular weight prediction) and gets reduced to get high molecular binding. The compound 6, 4 – Imidazolidinone, 1- (1,1 – dimethyl ethyl)-3- imino -5,5 – diph, Karisalankanni plant species showed its best binding pose for possible reduction of colon cancer and these can be used for therapeutic purposes in future studies.

- **Compound structures**

**Fig 5. Compound 1, 2 – Butanone, 4- (4-hydroxy– 3methoxyphenyl)-, Nilavembu
Presence of ligand [Left] in targeted molecule [Right]**

**Fig 6. Compound 14, 5- Oxazolecarboxamide, 4 – Methyl -, P.Polyphylla [Yellow
Stimulant]**

Presence of ligand [Left] in targeted molecule [Right]

**Fig 7. Compound 54, beta –D-Glucopyranose 1, 6 – anhydro, Aakaasa garudan
Presence of ligand [Left] in targeted molecule [Right]**

Fig 8. Compound 6, 4 – Imidazolidinone, 1- (1, 1 – dimethyl ethyl)-3- imino -5, 5 – diph, Karisalankanni powder

Presence of ligand [Left] in targeted molecule [Right]

6. CONCLUSION

Protein-based therapeutics is highly successful in clinic and currently enjoys unprecedented recognition of their potential. More than 100 genuine and similar number of modified therapeutic proteins are approved for clinical use in the European Union and the USA with 2010 sales of US\$108 bln; monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) accounted for almost half (48%) of the sales. Based on their pharmacological activity, they can be divided into five groups: (a) replacing a protein that is deficient or abnormal; (b) augmenting an existing pathway; (c) providing a novel function or activity; (d) interfering with a molecule or organism; and (e) delivering other compounds or proteins, such as a radionuclide, cytotoxic drug, or effector proteins. Therapeutic proteins can also be grouped based on their molecular types that include antibody-based drugs, Fc fusion proteins, anticoagulants, blood factors, bone morphogenetic proteins, engineered protein scaffolds, enzymes, growth factors, hormones, interferons, interleukins, and thrombolytics. They can also be classified based on their molecular mechanism of activity as (a) binding non-covalently to target, e.g., mAbs; (b) affecting covalent bonds, e.g., enzymes; and (c) exerting activity without specific interactions, e.g., serum albumin. Most protein therapeutics currently on the market is recombinant and hundreds of them are in clinical trials for therapy of cancers, immune disorders, infections, and other diseases. New engineered proteins, including bispecific mAbs and multispecific fusion proteins, mAbs conjugated with small molecule drugs, and proteins with optimized pharmacokinetics, are currently under development. However, in the last several decades, there are no conceptually new methodological developments comparable, e.g., to genetic engineering leading to the development of recombinant therapeutic proteins. It appears that a paradigm change in methodologies and understanding of mechanisms is needed to overcome major challenges, including resistance to therapy, access to targets, complexity of biological systems, and individual variations. [55]5EYF protein is considered as a therapeutic target because of its impact in many inflammatory diseases. Another interesting approach is that, this protein was chosen because of its higher binding affinity, which showed drug target with the compound 6 of Karisalankanni to give possible reduction in colon cancer cells using

computational modelling. Other compounds, are nearest to protein target but it shows not effective with *E. faecium* of 5EYF protein molecule. Drugs fail in the clinic for two main reasons; the first is that they do not work and the second is that they are not safe. As such, one of the most important steps in developing a new drug is target identification and validation. A target is a broad term which can be applied to a range of biological entities which may include for example proteins, genes and RNA. A good target needs to be efficacious, safe, meet clinical and commercial needs and, above all, be 'druggable'. A 'druggable' target is accessible to the putative drug molecule, be that a small molecule or larger biologicals and upon binding, elicit a biological response which may be measured both in vitro and in vivo. [56] This karisalankanni (4 – Imidazolidinone, 1- (1, 1 – dimethyl ethyl)-3- imino -5, 5 – diph) of ligand molecule show promises in the new perspective field of drug discovery.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- 1) <https://www.cancer.gov/about-cancer/understanding/what-is-cancer>
- 2) Parkin DM, Bray F, Ferlay J, Pisani P. Global cancer statistics, 2002. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2005; 55:74 –108.
- 3) Parkin DM. International variation. *Oncogene.* 2004; 23:6329 – 6340.
- 4) Center MM, Jemal A, Ward E. International trends in colorectal cancer incidence rates. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2009; 18:1688 –1694.
- 5) Giovannucci E, Wu K. Cancers of the colon and rectum. In: Schottenfeld D, Fraumeni J, eds. *Cancer Epidemiology and Prevention.* 3rd ed. New York: Oxford University Press; 2006:809–829.
- 6) Botteri E, Iodice S, Bagnardi V, et al. Smoking and colorectal cancer: a metaanalysis. *JAMA.* 2008; 300: 2765–2778.
- 7) Giovannucci E. Modifiable risk factors for colon cancer. *Gastroenterol Clin North Am.* 2002; 31:925–943.
- 8) Popkin BM. The nutrition transition: an overview of world patterns of change. *Nutr Rev.* 2004; 62:S140 – S143.
- 9) Hampel, H.; Frankel, W.L.; Martin, E.; Arnold, M.; Khanduja, K.; Kuebler, P.; Clendenning, M.; Sotamaa, K.; Prior, T.; Westman, J.A.; et al. Feasibility of screening for Lynch syndrome among patients with colorectal cancer. *J. Clin. Oncol.* 2008, 26, 5783–5788.
- 10) De Jong, A.E.; Morreau, H.; van Puijenbroek, M.; Eilers, P.H.; Wijnen, J.; Nagengast, F.M.; Griffioen, G.; Cats, A.; Menko, F.H.; Kleibeuker, J.H. The role of mismatch repair gene defects in the development of adenomas in patients with HNPCC. *Gastroenterology* 2004, 126, 42–48.
- 11) Warthin, A.S. Heredity with reference to carcinoma as shown by the study of the cases examined in the pathological laboratory of the University of Michigan, 1895–1913. *Arch. Intern. Med.* 1913, 12, 546–555.
- 12) Aaltonen, L.A.; Peltomaki, P.; Leach, F.S.; Sistonen, P.; Pylkkänen, L.; Mecklin, J.P.; Järvinen, H.; Powell, S.M.; Jen, J.; Hamilton, S.R.; et al. Clues to the pathogenesis of familial colorectal cancer. *Science* 1993, 260, 812–816.
- 13) Thibodeau, S.N.; Bren, G.; Schaid, D. Microsatellite instability in cancer of the proximal colon. *Science* 1993, 260, 816–819.
- 14) Ionov, Y.; Peinado, M.A.; Malkhosyan, S.; Shibata, D.; Perucho, M. Ubiquitous somatic mutations in simple repeated sequences reveal a new mechanism for colonic carcinogenesis. *Nature* 1993, 363, 558–561.

- 15) Fishel, R.; Kolodner, R.D. Identification of mismatch repair genes and their role in the development of cancer. *Curr. Opin. Genet. Dev.* 1995, 5, 382–395.
- 16) Libutti SK, Salz LB, Willett CG, Levine RA. Chapter 57: Cancer of the colon. In: DeVita VT, Lawrence TS, Rosenberg SA, eds. *DeVita, Hellman, and Rosenberg's Cancer: Principles and Practice of Oncology*. 10th ed. Philadelphia, Pa: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2015.
- 17) Tiwari AK, Roy HK, Lynch HT. Lynch Syndrome in the 21st Century: Clinical Perspectives. *QJM*. 2015 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/26224055>.
- 18) Medical Review-Christina Chun, MPH February 12, 2019 — Written by MaryAnn DePietro <https://www.healthline.com/health/colorectal-cancer/stages-of-colon-cancer#classifications>
- 19) Activation of phosphoinositide-3 kinase (PI-3K) pathway constitutes one of the most important mechanisms that regulate important cellular functions such as gene expression, cell cycle progression, cell growth, and differentiation [Dygas and Baranska, 2001].
- 20) Dygas A, Baranska J. 2001. Lipids and signal transduction in the nucleus. *Acta Biochim Pol* 48: 541– 549.
- 21) Torre LA, Bray F, Siegel RL, Ferlay J, Lortet-Tieulent J and Jemal A: Global cancer statistics, 2012. *CA Cancer J Clin* 65: 87-108, 2015.
- 22) Tao Liu and Hongli Yin, *Oncology Reports* 37: 193-200, 2017 on PDK1 promotes tumor cell proliferation and migration by enhancing the Warburg effect in non-small cell lung cancer.
- 23) Kaplon J, Zheng L, Meissl K, Chaneton B, Selivanov VA, Mackay G, van der Burg SH, Verdegaal EM, Cascante M, Shlomi T, et al: A key role for mitochondrial gatekeeper pyruvate dehydrogenase in oncogene-induced senescence. *Nature* 498: 109-112, 2013.
- 24) Sutendra G, Kinnaird A, Dromparis P, Paulin R, Stenson TH, Haromy A, Hashimoto K, Zhang N, Flaim E and Michelakis ED: A nuclear pyruvate dehydrogenase complex is important for the generation of acetyl-CoA and histone acetylation. *Cell* 158: 84-97, 2014.
- 25) Sutendra G and Michelakis ED: Pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase as a novel therapeutic target in oncology. *Front Oncol* 3: 38, 2013.
- 26) Hur H, Xuan Y, Kim YB, Lee G, Shim W, Yun J, Ham IH and Han SU: Expression of pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase-1 in gastric cancer as a potential therapeutic target. *Int J Oncol* 42:44-54, 2013.
- 27) Schell JC, Olson KA, Jiang L, Hawkins AJ, Van Vranken JG, Xie J, Egnatchik RA, Earl EG, DeBerardinis RJ and Rutter J: A role for the mitochondrial pyruvate carrier as a repressor of the Warburg effect and colon cancer cell growth. *Mol Cell* 56:400-413, 2014.
- 28) Qin L, Tian Y, Yu Z, Shi D, Wang J, Zhang C, Peng R, Chen X, Liu C, Chen Y, et al: Targeting PDK1 with dichloroacetophenone to inhibit acute myeloid leukemia (AML) cell growth. *Oncotarget* 7: 1395-1407, 2016.
- 29) Fong MY, Zhou W, Liu L, Alontaga AY, Chandra M, Ashby J, Chow A, O'Connor ST, Li S, Chin AR, et al: Breastcancer- secreted miR-122 reprograms glucose metabolism in premetastatic niche to promote metastasis. *Nat Cell Biol* 17:183-194, 2015.
- 30) Yang W, Zheng Y, Xia Y, Ji H, Chen X, Guo F, Lyssiotis CA, Aldape K, Cantley LC and Lu Z: ERK1/2-dependent phosphorylation and nuclear translocation of PKM2 promotes the Warburg effect. *Nat Cell Biol* 14: 1295-1304, 2012.
- 31) Meijer TW, Kaanders JH, Span PN and Bussink J: Targeting hypoxia, HIF-1, and tumor glucose metabolism to improve radiotherapy efficacy. *Clin Cancer Res* 18: 5585-5594, 2012.

- 32) Gilkes DM, Bajpai S, Chaturvedi P, Wirtz D and Semenza GL: Hypoxia-inducible factor 1 (HIF-1) promotes extracellular matrix remodeling under hypoxic conditions by inducing P4HA1, P4HA2, and PLOD2 expression in fibroblasts. *J Biol Chem* 288:10819-10829, 2013.
- 33) Li J, Xu Y, Long X-D, Wang W, Jiao HK, Mei Z, Yin QQ, Ma LN, Zhou AW, Wang LS, et al: Cbx4 governs HIF-1 α to potentiate angiogenesis of hepatocellular carcinoma by its SUMO E3 ligase activity. *Cancer Cell* 25: 118-131, 2014.
- 34) Pullamsetti SS, Banat GA, Schmall A, Szibor M, Pomagruk D, Hänze J, Kolosionek E, Wilhelm J, Braun T, Grimminger F, et al: Phosphodiesterase-4 promotes proliferation and angiogenesis of lung Cancer by crosstalk with HIF. *Oncogene* 32: 1121-1134, 2013.
- 35) Morris GM, Huey R, Lindstrom W, Sanner MF, Belew RK, Goodsell DS, Olson AJ. AutoDock4 and AutoDockTools4: Automated docking with selective receptor flexibility. *J Comput Chem.* 2009; 30:2785–2791.
- 36) Morris GM, Goodsell DS, Halliday RS, Huey R, Hart WE, Belew RK, Olson AJ. Automated docking using a Lamarckian genetic algorithm and an empirical binding free energy function. *J. Comp. Chem.* 1998; 19:1639–1662.
- 37) Morris GM, Goodsell DS, Huey R, Olson AJ. Distributed automated docking of flexible ligands to proteins: parallel applications of AutoDock 2.4. *J Comput Aided Mol Des.* 1996; 10:293–304.
- 38) Goodsell DS, Morris GM, Olson AJ. Automated docking of flexible ligands: applications of AutoDock. *J Mol Recognit.* 1996; 9:1–5.
- 39) Beuscher AE, Olson AJ. Iterative docking strategies for virtual ligand screening. In: Stroud RM, Finer-Moore J, editors. *Computational and Structural Approaches to Drug Discovery*. London: RSC Publishing; 2007. pp. 242–264.
- 40) Leach AR, Shoichet BK, Peishoff CE. Prediction of protein-ligand interactions. Docking and scoring: successes and gaps. *J. Med. Chem.* 2006; 49:5851–5855.
- 41) Coupez B, Lewis RA. Docking and scoring--theoretically easy, practically impossible? *Curr. Med. Chem.* 2006; 13:2995–3003.
- 42) Sousa SF, Fernandes PA, Ramos MJ. Protein-ligand docking: current status and future challenges. *Proteins.* 2006; 65:15–26.
- 43) Mohan V, Gibbs AC, Cummings MD, Jaeger EP, DesJarlais RL. Docking: successes and challenges. *Curr. Pharm. Des.* 2005; 11:323–333.
- 44) Kitchen DB, Decornez H, Furr JR, Bajorath J. Docking and scoring in virtual screening for drug discovery: methods and applications. *Nature Rev. Drug Discov.* 2004;3:935–949.
- 45) Brooijmans N, Kuntz ID. Molecular recognition and docking algorithms. *Annu. Rev. Biophys. Biomol. Struct.* 2003; 32:335–373.
- 46) Taylor RD, Jewsbury PJ, Essex JW. A review of protein-small molecule docking methods. *J. Comp. Aided Mol. Design.* 2002; 16: 151–166.
- 47) Halperin I, Ma B, Wolfson H, Nussinov R. Principles of docking: and overview of search algorithms and a guide to scoring functions. *Proteins: Struct. Funct. Genet.* 2002;47: 409–443.
- 48) Smolle M., Prior A.E., Brown A.E., Cooper A., Byron O. and Lindsay J.G. (2006) A new level of architectural complexity in the human pyruvate dehydrogenase complex. *J. Biol. Chem.* 281, 19772–19780.
- 49) Kolobova E., Tuganova A., Boulatnikov I. and Popov K.M. (2001) Regulation of pyruvate dehydrogenase activity through phosphorylation at multiple sites. *Biochem. J.* 358, 69–77.

- 50) Tovar-Mendez A., Hirani T.A., Miernyk J.A. and Randall D.D. (2005) Analysis of the catalytic mechanism of pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase. *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.* 434, 159–168.
- 51) Connaughton S., Chowdhury F., Attia R.R., Song S., Zhang Y., Elam M.B. et al. (2010) Regulation of pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase isoform 4 (PDK4) gene expression by glucocorticoids and insulin. *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.* 315, 159–167.
- 52) Martha J. Kuntz, Robert A. Harris, Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Indiana University School of Medicine Indianapolis, USA.
- 53) Sharma Revati, Chapagain Bipin, Pai (Bhat) Chitra, Bhattacharjee Minaksh, In vitro antibacterial activity of seven Indian spices against high level gentamicin resistant strains of enterococci, *Arch Med Sci*, 2015;11(4): 863–868.
- 54) Sharma P, McClees SF, Afaq F. Pomegranate for Prevention and Treatment of Cancer: An Update. *Molecules*. 2017 Jan 24; 22(1):177.
- 55) Dimitrov DS. Therapeutic proteins. *Methods Mol Biol*. 2012; 899:1-26.
- 56) Yang Y, Adelstein SJ, Kassis AI. Target discovery from data mining approaches. *Drug Discov Today*. 2009; 14:147–154.